

THE LEADERSHIP STYLE INFLUENCE OF NU JUNTINYUAT SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The success of an educational institution cannot be separated from the role of the principal in leading and managing the institution. The principal's leadership style is the key to success of the school. One of them can be seen from the effectiveness of the school management system. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the principal's leadership style on the effectiveness of school management. This research focuses on Juntinyuat High School (SMA) which is accredited A by the Ministry of Education (MoE). Data collection was carried out by field studies and supported by literature studies. Then, qualitative descriptive analysis was used to find the right conclusions. The results showed that most of the principals adhered to a democratic leadership style. There is a significant influence between the principal's leadership styles on school performance at the national level. The teachers and employees at the school feel cared for and guided by the principal who has a nurturing spirit. With a leadership style that suits the school community, a series of learning processes can take place well and neatly.

Keywords: principal influence, leadership style, school management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The principal or principal often plays the role of leader and manager. According to Abdul Aziz (2000), they are professional leaders who carry out two complementary roles, namely leadership and management. The principal is the fundamental leader in the school and on his shoulders rests the hopes of parents, students, teachers, society and government. (Mulyasa, 2009) believes that principals are a key element in improving the quality of education in schools so as to make them the most important individuals in school organizations. Simultaneously heavy workloads are unavoidable and as a result such circumstances can cause many principals to fail to manage and run schools effectively.

The principal is the most responsible person in the school whether it is related to the management, administration or implementation of all school policies and practices (Ramaiah, 1999). A great teacher really needs leadership qualities to manage and manage schools to smooth school management in order to create a quality generation. Likewise, the effective implementation of all policies with effective and innovative education at the school level, is in dire need of effective teacher leadership.

Principals must be forward-looking, proactive and dare to make changes to the interests and futures of students in the development and Punctuality, then guide and work to boost the school's capacity to its peak (Zain, 1996). (Mahmood, 1993) argues that the success of schools lies in the hands of teachers. This means that teachers must have various abilities, in addition to having the ability to teach, they can be role models and guidelines for teachers. Teachers must also be able to interpret changes in schools, be skilled in using relevant and accurate

leadership styles in different situations, be able to motivate teachers, staff and students to be more interested and committed to school affairs and activities. In the context of schools, it is very important that schools are led by competent leaders whose influence is very important for the achievement of educational institutions.

The success of a school depends on many factors, which include teachers, students, facilities and learning environment. Smart students, for example, undoubtedly contribute to school performance, as do dedicated teachers and adequate school facilities. However, research shows that the leadership quality of principals can have a very large influence on the quality and success of schools, student performance and teacher abilities.

1.1 Leadership style

Each institution has a head to lead the way to achieve the goals of the institution. Different leadership styles can affect the effectiveness or performance of school management. Leadership is a social influence process in which the leader seeks the voluntary participation of subordinates in an effort to achieve organizational goals (Omolayo, 2007). A leader can be defined as a person who delegates or influences others to act to carry out certain goals. Today few organizations need effective leaders who truly understand the complexities of a fast-paced world global environmental change.

If the task is highly structured and the leader has a good relationship with the employees, effectiveness will be high on the part of the employees. Organizational commitment and job satisfaction have a positive effect on organizational commitment and work performance on the principal's leadership style (Fang, Chang, & Chen, 2009). Mechanisms of leadership style influencing team innovation in schools. (Thomas, 1978) identified three main types of principals.

1. Director who manages administrative and educational content.
2. Administrator who let the teacher manage educational content and teaching methods while he/she manages other school matters.
3. Facilitators who support and assist teachers and are more interested in the process and not the procedure.

Based on (Lim et al., 2016) said that several leadership characteristics for the leadership style of principals to become superior principals include:

1. Types of principal's leadership style.
2. Knowledge and thinking.
3. Collaboration.
4. Motivation and encouragement
5. Curriculum and leadership empowerment in the workplace.

1.2 School management

Basically, education is one of the no one created development and progress civilization as well as enhancement quality life society. Quality of learning process Becomes part from reject measuring success something school. One of them is marked with how management school that implemented with good.

Management school means everything something related with management of the educational process for reach goals that have been set in period time short, medium nor does objective in period Long time, in a broad sense management have the meaning of planning, implementing, and supervising source power organization for reach objective by efficient and effective.

Whereas by narrow has the meaning of planning school programs, implementing school programs, leadership head schools /madrasahs, supervisors/evaluators, and information systems school / madrasa. School become a formal institution having role develop potency customer educate including aspect psychomotor, cognitive, and affective.

By general there is empathy function management known by the public namely:

1. Function planning (planning)
2. Function organizing (organizing)
3. Function directing (directing)
4. Function control (control)

Management school is part from Education management that regulates the arrangement source power people, curriculum, facilities, and resources shopping and funds as well effort reach objective school by flexible and dynamic. In Constitution number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, formulated national education goals namely " development " potency participant educate to be man believe, have faith for almighty god one, have character noble, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic citizens as well as responsible.

Quality something school determined by all inhabitant school including power education and energy educator as well as role main from head school. A head school Becomes key determine direction school that. Head school as director main how is the learning process teaching and caring administration orderly accomplished.

According to Wahjosumidjo (2011) explained in detail simple head school could defined as a power functional teacher given Duty addition for lead something institution or school where implementation of the learning process teach, or the place where occur interaction between teachers who give lessons and students who receive lessons ".

2. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the principal's leadership style on the effectiveness of school management. The research design for this research is a literature study and interviews with participants. According to Kerlinger (1986), developing a research design is a very important process so that researchers can answer the research questions posed and the objectives outlined. Data were collected and analyzed using qualitative descriptive analysis. As previously stated, one of the main objectives of this study is to find out the leadership style practiced at SMA NU Juntinyuat. This study uses a qualitative approach where the school is accredited as a superior school based on class A.

2.1 Participant

Several academics were involved in this research. The participants were teachers, employees and several students at SMA NU Juntinyuat. Data was collected by interviewing participants. In this paper the researcher thinks anonymous data collection will make young students and all participants more comfortable to answer questions at the interview because they do not have to worry about their careers and their own results. So, he did not identify the participants through several trials. In addition, students are involved to enrich the information that researchers need.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 NU Juntinyuat High School Biography

NU Juntinyuat High School is one of the school private below shade Ministry of Education and Culture of Indonesia. Located on Jalan KH. asyim Asyari number 1/1 Segeran KIDUL district j untinyuat district Indramayu , West Java. NU Juntinyuat High School in the beginning named SMA Yabujah (Yayasan Ibu Haji Chodijah), which was established in 1986, which was founded by the Ibu Hj Foundation. Chodijah as advanced program foundation after Yabujah Junior High School graduation in 1981. Then after 2 years walk in effort guard the existence of Yabujah High School in order to survive, then Ms. Hj. Foundation Manager Chodijah stage work same with Branch Representative Council Manager Nahdlatul Ulama District Juntinyuat (MWC NU) for making Yabujah High School operational by MWC NU Kec. Juntinyuat and still permanent is at in under the auspices of the Ibu Hj Foundation. Chodijah, then change Yabujah high school name became NU Juntinyuat High School in 1988 School ever at NU Juntinyuat High School is as following:

1. RAYUNO from 1986 to year 1987
2. H. Mas'ud from year 1987 to 1988
3. Mustafid, BA from 1988 to 1989
4. Abas Assafah AD, S.Ag. , M. Si from 1989 to 2009
5. Burhanudin, M.Pd.I from 2009 to 2021
6. Novi Assirotunnabawiyah, SE from 2021 until now

As for the vision that is owned by the school this, namely "Making" NU Juntinyuat High School As an Educational Institution That Is Able To Deliver Inhabitant learn it To the Path of Happiness in this World and the Hereafter"

Temporary the mission you want achieved is as following:

- Enthusiasm Inside for Self Be the Best
- COOPERATIVE With Various party good direct nor no direct
- Taqwa to Allah whenever and wherever
- SCIENTIFIC Inside Think And Act
- PROFESSIONAL IN line Task Principal and Function

Quality graduate school vocational description for fulfil standard competence in the world of work. One of them, apart from capable dominates ingredients lessons, students should could interactive and active in connection social. Activity extracurricular is one tool introduction student in relationship social. In it there is education introduction self and development ability besides that understanding ingredients lesson.

Apart from student council as parent activity extracurricular at school, activities extracurricular other is:

- Scout
- Flag raises
- Youth Red Cross (PMR)
- Art
- Nature lovers (PA)
- Sports (Volleyball, Basketball, Karate, Tennis Table, Tennis field)

Following is description schools and activities at NU Juntinyuat High School:

Figure 1: NU Juntinyuat High School activities

3.1 The influence of leadership style on school management

could not denied that success a school no miss from role head leading school _ as well as move whole component. Based on from the results of the discussion, this study found that the principal's leadership style has an effect on school management. Head school at NU Juntinyuat truly pay attention to the implementation process study teach as well as correct administration. Head school own attitude protect to citizen school. Every one month very head school to do checking and monitoring to correct administration. When a teacher experiences obstacles in Thing administration as well as the learning process, head school the no disinclined for help him. Following is chart integration among leadership a head school with management. One of the teachers said that style leadership at NU Juntinyuat High School very democratic no dictator. Leader always hear aspirations of teachers and the academic community. The point is that the head of the madrasa here who has a democratic attitude is done by discussing first with his subordinates about a problem. This shows the leader's attitude towards transformational leadership because it means considering needs led by needs above personal needs. As a school

leader, the principal must be able to overcome various problems, be able to think analytically and conceptually, must always act as a mediator in solving problems faced by teachers, and always try to make decisions that can satisfy everyone. To achieve academic excellence, principals need to act intelligently and systematically so that the planned strategies can be implemented efficiently. Furthermore, school principals must be able to influence school staff to continue to make changes. Leading a school can be a very challenging job. Thus, a leader must be creative, knowledgeable and willing to implement and accept changes, especially for improving student performance. As illustrated in the results, most of the principals at Juntinyuat NU pay attention to the performance and achievements of their students, emphasize the importance of discipline in their schools, are willing to help teachers to be more effective, especially in the teaching-learning process.

This can be seen from the data analysis which shows that most of the principals are qualified, open-minded, knowledgeable and able to make decisions. A study by (MØller et al., 2007) also show that values such as encouragement, fairness in schools or in society can produce successful democratic leaders. Many teachers and staff at SMA NU Juntinyuat admitted to agree and feel comfortable with this leadership style. They work without tension and do not experience high levels of physiological stress. This is due to the leadership style applied by the principal in this school. (Hoy & Smith, 2007) argue that the single most important factor in school effectiveness is the principal. This statement illustrates the need for leaders to recognize their leadership style and have an understanding of how important it is to the overall effectiveness of their school. The leadership style which is mostly practiced by school administrators plays an integral role in the proper functioning of all aspects of the school.

Figure 2: Integration management and leadership

From the number 1 can take information that several factors that make school own management good school blessing leadership a head school. Own character leadership as following:

1. A head school should own strategic thinking ability. Strategies that think about here is a strategy for advance school with manage participant students, teachers and power educator as well as activities school so more interesting and always up to date.

2. Leading direction culture

A head schools that have character as this will capable direct whole power educator nor power education for proceed together. No only manage teachers and staff, but also be able to direct habits good to be culture school that.

3. Manage resources

Source power is meant here more emphasized for source power the human inside school that. How head school organizes and manage source power people at school the in accordance with ability every individual. So that everyone in school will work in accordance with abilities and fields skill they

4. Manage quality

Management quality will produce reputation school, so a leader who has characteristics this wills always new quality. When one school own good quality so will many parents participant learner who trusts her son for school at the Institute. Repair quality started from head school that alone until whole inhabitant school.

5. Manage projects

Every school naturally owns various projects, such as well as SMA NU Juntinyuat which has various Suite activity yearly. As follow race Scouts, Olympics science and competition religious. As a leader should own character capable managing ongoing projects in progress to use get satisfactory results.

6. Manage information

Every information submitted from government center must be distributed to whole inhabitant school with clear and accurate. The information submitted must also be delivered at the right time. Don't until information late be delivered so that both teachers and participant educate no can follow something activity because not enough preparation consequence present late information.

7. Manage activities

No denial that NU Juntinyuat School own lots of activity as existence many kinds of extracurricular. Head school own role as person responsible answer should capable manage activity total activity extracurricular so can walk with good. Because extracurricular is receptacle for develop interests and talents participant educate.

8. Manage and lead people

A head school should own characteristics capable manage and lead people. No only people working inside office school that, but also able build and lead participant educate. Keith and (Keith & Girling, 1991) research in 16 high schools in California where schools with leaders who care and have good relationships with students ultimately produce students who perform very well.

The influence of leadership style on school management

Leadership style in high school is a critical issue in creating a school culture where teachers and all education personnel are satisfied with their work. Finally they can change the changing traditional culture into a modern and dynamic school. As discussed by (Hauserman & Stick, 2013), teachers' perceptions of highly transformational principals result in teachers being happier with school leadership and more willing to put in more effort in their work.

1. Communication with the school community

An important leadership trait that is integral to a successful leader is communication. It is very important to have transparent communication between teachers and people in their vertical structure. So that teachers feel supported and their voices heard. When the teacher is not listened to, feelings of dissatisfaction, frustration and tension arise which ultimately lead to a toxic atmosphere (Healey, 2009). Highly effective leaders make effective communication a priority and ensure that teachers are comfortable having bold conversations about their practice. Transformational leaders place communication at the forefront of their leadership practice, thereby making their teachers comfortable with bold conversation. Finally, they are happy to do their job to improve school management.

2. good administration

Every institution, including SMA NU Juntinyuat cannot be separated from administrative compliance. Completeness administration Becomes reject measuring something school orderly carry out Duty they every school own a supervisor who will always do checking to completeness administration school. Because of things this will show quality from school that alone as well as Reflects the leadership style of the principle.

3. Academic achievement

Management good school will bring supportive atmosphere and environment for development participant educate. NU Juntinyuat High School own various performance blessing democratic leadership. Participant educate feel comfortable and comfortable be at school.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that the democratic style is the right style to lead a great school management. The researchers also found that there was a need for an integrated leadership model. Through an intensive review of the leadership

literature, it is evident that leadership style plays an integral role in positive educational outcomes and the creation of a positive school culture. Good communication, orderly administration, and instructional leadership styles all have very important characteristics in an effective leader and can be integrated effectively to maximize the potential of school administration's human resources. Due to its dynamic and ever-changing nature, leadership in schools also has a great influence on school management and student learning. Educators who enjoy their work will have an increased level of organizational commitment, which has great benefits for students. Leaders who have an integrated, first-person leadership style and are truly committed to the well-being of their staff have the greatest influence on the positive culture in their schools.

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